

Building a Sustainable Future: Leveraging University Resources for FabLab Development and Community Engagement

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Abstract

The development of students' methodological and practical skills in complex problem-solving processes and their ability to learn and work collaboratively must be specifically promoted. To this end, students should be given the opportunity to work in (interdisciplinary) teams on the development of prototypes or to carry out their own projects. In order to successfully implement the special didactic scenarios required for this, a suitable and flexible design of learning spaces and resource management is necessary.

The "blended makerspace" concept was developed to make learning spaces and workshops easy to use and accessible for students. Realized as FabLab@TU-Ilmenau, resources and completed projects of various stakeholders are now centrally described, access options explained and reservation options provided. This work is being driven forward as part of the examING1 and Ilmkubator2 projects at TU Ilmenau within the years 2022 - 2024.

Keywords

FabLab, collaboration, university library, sustainability, student workshop, future skills, start-up service, education, community, entrepreneurship

1 Motivation for gaining application-orientated experience during studies

Engineers have to create efficient and effective solutions for complex technical problems and develop future-oriented technologies. The way engineers work is increasingly characterized by interdisciplinary and agile processing of projects in teams. Problem-solving skills, creativity, entrepreneurial thinking and action as well as the ability to engage in dialogue and conflict resolution are relevant skills for this. Enabling activating and motivating learning situations at universities is therefore an important institutional task and challenge in order to equip students with the necessary skills to act independently and competently, to continue learning and to be innovative and creative after graduation, in addition to providing an excellent academic education. This is also important with regard to the "employability" required by

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the European Commission (Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture (European Commission), 2019).

1.1 Framework conditions in engineering education at the TU Ilmenau

Every student at TU Ilmenau is given the opportunity to gain practical experience in the use of special technologies as well as in development processes and project- and team- work in different contexts right from the start of their studies and to benefit from expert support:

- At TU Ilmenau, the "Gemeinsame ingenieurwissenschaftliche Grundlagenstudium" (GiG) — Joint basic engineering studies — allows students to start their engineering studies across all degree programs.
- Subject-related and curriculum-based formats of project-oriented learning in teams e.g. in the form of software projects, project seminars, design assignments—offer opportunities for skills development, especially in higher semesters.
- The trialing of the BASIC teaching concept (<https://www.tu-ilmenau.de/basic>) led to additional offers in practical engineering training, especially for the introductory phase of studies (Geigenmüller et al., 2021).

1.2 Challenges in the implementation

Challenges arise in the design of authentic and appealing learning spaces. These should be flexibly accessible and usable and support effective team and project work. Existing classrooms were therefore gradually expanded and further developed.

The aim is to create transparent access for practical engineering and project-orientated learning opportunities. After a brief explanation of our didactic considerations (section 2), we describe the decentralized resources (section 3). The "Blended Makerspace" concept was developed in the examING project to support and utilize the learning locations (Chapter 4). The following section presents our implementation as FabLab@TU-Ilmenau.

2 Didactic concepts

In order to achieve the development of the competences described above, learning situations must be created that - in the sense of enabling didactics (Quilling, 2015) - offer students the necessary freedom to get involved themselves, to try things out in a positive error culture, and to test and consolidate acquired knowledge in practical projects. In this way, they learn to "deal competently with technology and move from being passive consumers to self-confident producers" (Bergner, 2017).

In order to anchor these concepts even more purposefully in curricular teaching for Bachelor's engineering students in the future, the examING project at TU Ilmenau (www.tu-ilmenau.de/examing, see also chapter 4) is working on expanding the range of options for providing competence-orientated engineering-specific coursework, testing new settings and further developing the necessary infrastructure. Figure 1, based on the Constructive Alignment concept (Biggs & Tang, 2011), illustrates the categorization of the tasks worked on in the project.

Figure 1: Requirements for engineering education based on the constructive alignment concept

In the implementation, we rely on a basic infrastructure with a network of learning spaces that promotes practical, project-orientated work across different disciplines. Inspired by the FabLab's and the maker movement (Gershenfeld, 2006), various open labs are being created that are networked with each other and provide learners with the necessary tools, machines and workstations for a wide range of projects and objectives (see chapter 5).

FabLab's are therefore, on the one hand, places of making, where things are created, but also places of exchange, learning, cooperation and transfer. On the other hand, users learn through the experience of making something themselves. They mentor each other and acquire valuable knowledge about machines, materials, design processes and the technology that goes into inventions and innovations, as described by the Fab Foundation (Fab Foundation, 2023). The interplay between the three major areas of Make - Learn - Share is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Interaction of the FabLab areas Make, Learn and Share

Studies have already shown that FabLab's have a positive influence on team communication and students' self-efficacy (Andrews & Roberts, 2017) and have a positive impact on the overall study result (Hilton et al., 2018).

3 Places of practical training

This section provides an insight into the variety of decentralized actors that provide students with practical engineering learning opportunities on campus - in addition to the curricular internships and opportu-

nities to build prototypes in the laboratories. These existing, established structures are activated and made transparently accessible to students.

UNIKAT is a student-initiated and managed workshop for pupils and students that is accessible around the clock. Located in the central campus area, it can be used for the realization of own projects and ideas as well as for exchange among "makers". Special workshops and events are also offered, e.g. on topics such as 3D printing, soldering, Arduino programming, working with special machines, as well as professionally supervised opening hours (Open Lab).

<https://www.tu-ilmenau.de/en/university/quicklinks/central-institute-for-continuing-education/offers/unikat>

The training workshop also offers workshops, e.g. in the field of turning and milling for students and members of the university, as well as supporting students' projects in the field of mechanics.

<https://www.tu-ilmenau.de/en/university/quicklinks/central-institute-for-continuing-education/education/training-workshop>

Another multifunctional teaching and learning space have been created in the university library: the Learning World. Since its completion, it has been used for project-based learning with groups of different sizes and compositions.

<https://www.tu-ilmenau.de/en/university/quicklinks/university-library/learn-work/workspaces/special-working-areas-1>

With the *practicING* programs, engineering students in particular can expand their studies with additional practical courses right from the start. The programs are designed to be interdisciplinary. Participants are accompanied and supported by specialist departments, teaching groups and student tutors across all structures. Topics range from supplementary experiments, practical seminars and workshops to complex interdisciplinary projects in teams.

<https://www.tu-ilmenau.de/en/university/quicklinks/central-institute-for-continuing-education/education/practicing-by-basic>

As a start-up service, the Ilmenau Ideas Incubator (Ilmkubator for short) offers students, doctoral students and employees of TU Ilmenau the opportunity to learn entrepreneurial thinking and action in a targeted manner. In line with the Entrepreneurial Skills Charter (2023), future-oriented skills such as visionary thinking, creativity and cooperation are trained, as well as working in interdisciplinary teams and the ability to mobilize resources. The learning and working spaces located on the edge of the campus area are used for workshops, start-up coaching as co-working and creative spaces and for the production of prototypes, for example. EXIST start-up scholarship holders, EXIST research transfer measures and the work of participants in the Ilmkubator classes are particularly supported here.

<https://www.tu-ilmenau.de/en/ilmkubator/page>

Many students also take advantage of the participation opportunities offered by regionally active associations, such as "Engineers without Borders" with regular offers such as repair meetings, etc., Team Starcraft e.V., the University Radio (hsf), the Research Association for Electronic Media e.V. (FEM).

4 Approach in the examING project

The examING project aims to develop innovative, digitally supported and student-centered ideas for competency-oriented exams/study achievements for engineering bachelor's degree programs and to bring them into university practice.

The focus is particularly on innovative approaches to further developing the necessary infrastructure to sustainably anchor the tried and tested concepts. A so-called "Blended Makerspace" concept was developed for this purpose. This means that the introductory and orientation phase for using the FabLab offers is digitally mapped. The project is then implemented on site in the various workshops and work

spaces. Finished projects can then be presented and shared in this digital space, and further offers such as start-up support can be used.

The "Blended Makerspace" concept thus helps to compensate for the special situation at the university with the distributed laboratories by bringing them together digitally, highlighting the special offers at the various locations and providing a common booking platform. The following section five describes the current status of the implementation of this concept on the basis of a FabLab specially adapted to Ilmenau's requirements.

5 FabLab@TU-Ilmenau

Collaborative physical platforms, open workshops, hacker or maker spaces, FabLab's, repair cafés, etc. have seen a strong increase in recent years and can be seen as pioneers for transformative economic developments (Lange, 2017). According to Aryan (Aryan et al., 2021), FabLab's offer a good basis for a new networked social structure. The investment costs for equipping a FabLab (*FabLab Charter*, 2012) with the necessary machines and tools amount to around €100,000 (Troxler, 2014).

It was determined that a large part of the infrastructure at the TU Ilmenau is physically present, but is spread across the entire campus. The aim of those involved was to make these resources visible and thus enable them to be used in as many different ways as possible. The transparency of the offers makes it possible to create individual support scenarios, for example for start-up teams from the MINT subjects, who can use various workshops, laboratories and infrastructures to build prototypes.

This involves intensive cooperation between the learning center operators. In regular meetings with all stakeholders, current developments, wishes and needs were and are exchanged, feasible concepts are developed and implemented independently and step by step. The process can also be viewed as commons-based peer production (Benkler & Nissenbaum, 2006), since all participants have always decided independently which of the required activities they can take on and which contributions they want to make.

5.1 The portal to the FabLab

With a central digital entry point, processes of the "Blended Makerspace" concept are mapped. This means:

Editorial functionalities are made available to providers:

- to describe the learning spaces (location, opening times, access, contact, equipment, instructions and instructions)
- to characterize individual machines and tools as well as experimental environments (e.g. 3D printers, laser and plotter cutting machines, microcontrollers)
- to offer tutorials and workshops
- options for checking occupancy and registrations

For users there are:

- entry and orientation areas for using the FabLab
- options for intuitive research in the offers
- a booking system for offers
- the possibility of presenting finished projects

- information on further offers (e.g. start-up service)

Figure 3: Screenshot of the digital presence of the FabLab@TU-Ilmenau

For the current implementation, after a comprehensive market analysis, the Fab Manager software (*Fab Manager*, 2023) is used as a basis and adapted to the specific needs of the decentralized locations. Adjustments have so far been necessary with regard to the payment system, room reservation and allocation. One challenge is to structure the offer descriptions in a user-friendly way. For this purpose, interviews were conducted with actors and user groups and catalogues for structuring, metadata and sample entries were provided.

The current version is hosted on <https://fablab.tu-ilmenau.de>. The content is being continuously expanded and the system is gradually being functionally expanded. The FabLab portal and the networking of the actors have already generated further ideas for practical offers. The participation of the students in the laboratories, who also work enthusiastically in the learning locations outside of their curriculum and present their projects, is very positive.

6 Conclusion and outlook

This article presented the implementation concepts at the TU Ilmenau for learning spaces for individually initiated project-oriented and practical learning. The core of the explanations was a site-specific "blended makerspace" concept to include decentralized actors and resources and to enable transparent and easy access. The implementation of the concept as FabLab@TU-Ilmenau was presented.

Feedback from teachers has shown that by realizing their own or proposed projects, students learn entrepreneurial thinking, exchange with others and work together. In doing so, they develop the ability to specify a goal that may initially be unclear, to divide it into necessary work and success steps, to implement them and to present them. Other teachers have already expressed an interest in using the creative and practical learning spaces.

Future work includes the continuous coordination of the FabLab, quality assurance and the further development of the system in accordance with technological and legal standards. It is possible to expand the scope to include specific offerings at the university's technological centers and affiliated institutes.

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